

STUDIES OF THE INTERFACE BETWEEN CARBON FIBRES AND ALUMINIUM ALLOYS IN

MELT-INFILTRATED SQUEEZE-CAST METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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Summary

Metal matrix composites have been prepared by infiltration of carbon-fibre preforms with molten aluminium alloys using moderate pressures in a squeeze-casting operation. It was found possible to fully infiltrate quite dense preforms. In the as-cast state, wetting of the fibres appeared to be excellent and there was no evidence of significant interface reaction. On heat treatment at temperatures of 550°C for extended times some degradation occurred, especially when the heat treatment was carried out in air. There was evidence of carbide formation in Al/Mg but not in Al/Si alloys, and it was observed that the fibre surfaces were more rapidly attacked in Al/Si than in Al/Mg.

Introduction

There is considerable interest in metal-matrix composites utilising carbon (graphite)-fibres in light-alloy matrices. The usefulness of these systems is limited by the high cost of the conventional powder-metallurgy based fabrication route, corrosion problems due to the very high electrochemical potential difference between the fibre and the matrix material, and poor mechanical properties transverse to the fibre direction. In PAN-based carbon fibres the graphitic layer planes are preferentially oriented circumferentially to the fibre axis at the fibre surface. This makes the fibres inherently weak in the transverse direction and difficult to wet with liquid metals, unless conditions allow some chemical reaction to occur at the interface. In the case of aluminium alloys a carbide, Al_4C_3 , is known to form at temperatures in excess of 550°C (1). The conventional fabrication route involves exposure to temperatures of this order for long periods. The interface reaction may be controlled by coating the fibres with a barrier layer, and this technique may also be used to improve wettability, but it adds further to the expense and complexity of the fabrication.

The objective of the present work was to explore the possibility of using a melt-infiltration fabrication technique, which should be not only cheaper and faster than the powder route, but might also avoid interface problems by limiting the residence time at high temperature.

Experimental

The basis of the fabrication technique is described in detail elsewhere (2,3). Essentially the fibre is made into a dry preform, which is then placed in the cavity of a simple cylindrical mould, which has been pre-heated to a temperature of about 300°C. Molten aluminium alloy is poured into the mould, on top of the preform, and then pressurised by means of a hydraulically operated ram. The pressurisation cycle takes only about 30s (and could be even less in a properly engineering squeeze-casting machine). Pouring temperatures were typically 100-150 deg C above the liquidus of the alloy, ie 750-850°C, and the infiltration pressure typically 15-20 MPa. Thus, although the maximum temperature of contact between the fibre and metal is considerably higher than 550°C, the total contact time need be only a few seconds.

The fibres used in the investigation were conventional "high-strength" and "high-modulus" PAN-based carbon fibre. The "high-strength" fibre was, however, manufactured some 10 years ago and its properties are not comparable with currently available fibres. The "high-modulus" fibre was of recent manufacture. Most of the material was in the form of 10 k tow, but some 6 mm chopped fibre and a woven cloth was also used. The fibre diameter was approximately 8 µm. Preforms were made by: stitching layers of cloth together with aluminium wire, by winding the tow onto a steel-wire frame, and by sandwiching lengths of tow, pieces of cloth, or layers of chopped-fibre between alumina-fibre preforms. (These alumina-preforms were the subject of a parallel investigation (2).) The basic objective was to infiltrate a small volume of carbon-fibre so that the interface could be studied. In practice the carbon-fibre in all the forms studied proved to infiltrate very readily. Preforms consisting of up to 10 layers of the cloth (5 mm total thickness) were fully infiltrated, but difficulties were experienced with thicker layers. The tow and chopped-fibre preforms were much less closely packed and no difficulty was experienced in achieving full infiltration.

The bulk of the investigation was conducted with two conventional aluminium casting alloys, a 12%Si eutectic alloy and a 10%Mg containing alloy. These were chosen on account of their low liquidus temperatures and because they had been used successfully to infiltrate alumina-preforms. A wider range of alloys will be used in future work.

After the casting/infiltration operation the billets were sectioned to isolate the carbon-fibre filled portions which were further sectioned for optical microscopy. Samples were also subjected to prolonged heat treatment at temperatures of up to 550°C for up to 10 days to assess their susceptibility to degradation and interface reactions. The reaction products in the composites were studied using electron probe microanalysis (EPMA) and by X-ray diffraction.

Results

Metallography of "as cast" billets

It was generally found that the fibre was rapidly and completely infiltrated to yield a "sound" billet with negligible porosity or unwetted regions. The only exceptions were in the case of thick (more than 5 mm) preforms made from the woven cloth. The cloth formed a much denser preform

100 μm

Fig 1. Low power micrograph of HM fibre in Al/Mg alloy, showing high fibre packing density.

20 μm

Fig 2. Cross-section of a HS-Al/Si composite. The fibres are well wetted and the eutectic silicon may be seen.

50 μm

Fig 3. Longitudinal section of the HS-Al/Si composite, showing the eutectic matrix.

50 μm

Fig 4. HS-Al/Mg composite. The fibres are well wetted and tightly bunched in some areas. A grain boundary may be seen running along the interface regions.

— 50 μ m

Fig 5. Cross-section of the HM-Al/Si material. The eutectic Si is more acicular in this casting.

Fig 6. SEM of an "as received" HS fibre surface. This is for comparison with those extracted from the cast billets.

Fig 7. SEM of a HS fibre exposed by etching an Al/Si casting. There is some degradation of the surface. Note the eutectic Si particles around the fibre.

Fig 8. SEM of a HS fibre exposed by etching the Al/Mg material. There is less attack than in the Al/Si alloy.

than the alternative methods used, which explains the relative difficulty in achieving full infiltration. The manufacture of cloth based composites was not the primary objective of the work, so no attempt was made to overcome this problem.

During the initial metallographic work it was noted that very high concentrations of fibre occurred in some regions of the composites. In some cases almost perfect hexagonal packing was observed (fig 1). This is presumably due to a strong interaction between the liquid metal and the fibre surface, which tends to draw the interfacial regions together. There was, however, no evidence of any reaction layer in the "as cast" materials.

Optical micrographs of composites made with the high-strength fibres and the two aluminium alloys are shown in figs 2-4. Both sets show good wetting and there is a suggestion that the eutectic silicon forms preferentially close to the fibres in the Al/Si alloy. The close-packing effect is more prominent in the case of the high-modulus fibre composites (fig 5), the silicon appears to be more acicular in these billets, but it is not known whether this is due to the different fibre, or to some variation in the cooling conditions. It was not possible to maintain identical conditions in every cast.

The fibre surfaces in the billets were examined by first deep-etching a polished surface in Keller's reagent and then using the SEM. There was little evidence of any surface change in the "as cast" materials. Figs 6 and 7 show a virgin high-strength fibre and one exposed by etching the Al/Si based composite. The eutectic Si particles are also revealed and, again evidence of preferential formation in the interface region may be seen. A fibre exposed in the Al/Mg alloy is shown in fig 8. It was not possible to detect any reaction layer at the interface by microscopy, EPMA or X-ray diffraction in either of the alloys.

A number of fibres were extracted from the cast billets by prolonged etching and then subjected to tensile test. The results of these tests are given in Table 1. These tests confirmed that there had been little attack on the fibres during the casting operation. The fibres extracted from the Al/Si alloy were marginally weakened.

Table 1

Tensile Strength of Carbon Fibres (GPa) (gauge length: 20 mm)

	HS Fibre	HM Fibre
as received	2.90	3.07
from Al/Si composite	2.56	2.91
from Al/Mg composite	3.24	3.05

Note: The HS Fibre is not typical of current fibres and was actually weaker than the HM fibre which is of recent manufacture.

20 μm

Fig 9. Cross-section of a HS-Al/Si composite, heat treated in air for 72 h. at 500°C. There is no evidence of any interface reaction, but the eutectic Si particles have grown considerably, cf. Fig 2.

Fig 10. SEM of a HS fibre exposed by etching the heat treated Al/Si alloy (Fig 9). Note the severe pitting attack at the fibre surface.

50 μm

Fig 11. HS-Al/Si composite, heat treated in air for 240 h. at 550°C. The fibres have been almost completely oxidised away. The large agglomerated eutectic Si particles are seen together with a dark-etching network which is thought to be oxide.

50 μm

Fig 12. HM-Al/Si composite, heat treated in air for 240 h. at 550°C. Apart from the coarsened Si particles there is little evidence of any interface reaction.

Effects of prolonged heat treatment

In order to assess the sensitivity of the composites to interface reactions a number of heat treatments were carried out. The temperatures used were 450, 500 and 550°C for times of up to 240 hours. The highest temperature was determined by the liquidus of the alloys (in fact some liquation was observed in the Al/Mg alloy at 550°C). Furnace atmospheres of air and argon were used.

In the case of the high-strength fibre in the Al/Si alloy, heated in air at temperatures of 500°C for 72 hours or 550°C for 24 hours, the only change observed was coarsening of the Si in the eutectic (fig 9). However, after 72 hours at 550°C and 240 hours at the other temperatures, some cracking, cavity formation, and fibre degradation was observed. The etching technique, described above, showed extensive attack of the fibre surfaces (fig 10). Essentially similar observations were made with the high-modulus fibres in the Al/Si alloy, except that the rate of degradation was marginally lower. After long periods at 550°C the fibres were sometimes observed to be completely destroyed by oxidation. An example is shown in Fig. 11.

The heat treatments were then repeated, but with an argon atmosphere. No fibre degradation or cavities were observed after 240 hours at 550°C. There appeared to have been no reaction at the interface. The only difference from the original condition was the growth of the Si particles (fig 12). No significant surface attack on the fibre was observed after deep etching. There was no evidence of carbide formation at the interface.

The behaviour of the Al/Mg based composites was somewhat different. Heat treatment in air caused little change until 72 hours at 550°C, or 240 hours at 500°C. Then a sporadic degradation of the fibres was seen (fig 13). This is attributed to oxidation of those fibres intersecting the surface, whilst fully "buried" fibres were unaffected. Deep-etching showed moderate attack of the fibre surface (fig 14), but the deep pits observed on fibres in the Al/Si alloy did not occur. After the most severe heat-treatment (240 hours at 550°C) the fibre was sometimes observed to have been completely destroyed.

On heat treatment in argon a second phase was observed to form around the fibres. This is shown in the optical micrograph of fig 15, and in the "deep-etched" SEM of fig 16. This phase has been identified, by X-ray diffraction, to be the aluminium carbide. Even so the surface of the fibre does not appear to have been heavily attacked.

Discussion

These preliminary experiments have established that carbon-fibre/aluminium-alloy composites may successfully be fabricated by the infiltration of fibre-preforms under moderate pressure. Both the high-strength and high-modulus fibres were fully infiltrated and completely wetted, and in neither case was any significant interface reaction zone observed in the "as cast" material.

50 μm

Fig 13. HS-Al/Mg alloy heat treated in air for 240 h. at 500°C. Some fibres have been severely oxidised. They are thought to be fibres which intersected an exposed surface during the treatment.

Fig 14. SEM of a fibre extracted from an Al/Mg alloy, heat treated in air for 24 h. at 550°C. There appears to have been significant attack at the fibre surface.

50 μm

Fig 15. HM-Al/Mg heat treated in argon for 240 h. at 550°C. The growth of Al_4C_3 plates around the fibres is clearly visible.

Fig 16. SEM of a HM fibre exposed by etching the specimen shown in Fig 15. The carbide particles may be seen around the fibre, which does not appear to have been severely attacked.

The heat treatment experiments show that the composites are reasonably stable for long periods at temperatures of up to 500°C. In oxidising atmospheres, however, the fibres are attacked quite severely at 500°C and above. The specimens used in these experiments were small (approx 10 mm cube), so it is not possible to comment on the rate of penetration of the oxidation. The high-modulus fibre containing materials were marginally less affected by the oxidation than the high-strength fibre materials.

There was some indication of preferential formation of the Si eutectic particles near the fibre surfaces in the Al/Si alloys. On heat treatment in air these fibres showed a characteristic pitted appearance, which was not evident in the Al/Mg composites. It seems probable that the presence of Si accelerates the rate of oxidative attack on the fibres. In the Al/Mg composites, however, aluminium carbide was formed after long heat treatments at 550°C. This confirms the trends reported by other workers (1,4,5). It is probable that this carbide layer at the interface would severely reduce the transverse mechanical properties. The fact that no detectable aluminium carbide was formed in the Al/Si alloy is possibly due to formation of a very thin silicon carbide barrier at the interface. There is however no positive evidence for this. We may conclude that both alloys appear to give composites which are reasonably stable at temperatures below 500°C in both neutral and oxidising atmospheres. Above this temperature oxidation effects are initially more severe in the Al/Si alloy, but in neutral atmospheres the reaction to form aluminium carbide is much faster in the Al/Mg alloy. It is possible that silicon may be useful to control the tendency to form the aluminium carbide.

No mechanical tests have been carried out on these composites in this first phase of the programme, apart from a limited amount of hardness testing. It was apparent, even from this, that the interface was quite weak and that unidirectionally reinforced material would readily split along the interface, parallel to the fibres. The tendency of parallel arrays of fibre to pack tightly during fabrication must increase this weakness. Even if a relatively strong interface were developed, the fibres themselves are very weak in the transverse direction and this must limit the possible transverse strength of any uniaxial composite. A superficial examination of several accidentally split specimens suggests that the fracture path ran through the fibres rather than in the interface region. Further work is in progress on this.

The previous remarks would suggest that the properties of high volume fraction, uniaxial composites of carbon-fibres in aluminium alloys must have severely limited transverse properties, which will limit their usefulness to a few very specialised applications. It is considered, however, that composites based on random arrays of short fibres may be more generally useful in general engineering applications. Such composites could be conveniently and economically manufactured by the squeeze-infiltration process used in this work.

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References

1. K. Motoki and A. Okura, in "Progress in Science and Engineering of Composites" eds T. Hayashi et al. Proc. ICCM 4 Tokyo (1982) 1281-1287.
2. T.W. Clyne, M.G. Bader, G.R. Cappleman and P.A. Hubert, J.Mater.Sci., Vol. 20 (1985), 85.
3. T.W. Clyne and M.G. Bader, Proc. ICCM V, AIME, San Diego, 1985 (in press).
4. G. Blankenburgs, J.Aust.Inst. of Metals, Vol. 14 (1969), 236.
5. A.A. Baker, C. Shipman and P.W. Jackson, Fibre Sci.Tech., Vol. 5 (1982), 213.